

Role of Communication and Soft Skills on Administration

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ABSTRACT

Communication & Soft skills have emerged as the most powerful set of skills to possess for accelerating one's career need and speed of accomplishment in every walk of life. To prepare your selves for a rewarding career in the broad field of administration and management, it is even more essential to acquire, practice and exhibit high levels of communication skills in normal and crisis situations. The main reason for choosing this topic for paper, was realizing how important communication is in school administration. Being able to keep a fluent conversation is viewed as the main goal of all students, teaching and non teaching staff, which underlines the importance of speaking skills with student's & employees. Teacher leaders help direct the entire school toward higher standards of achievement and recognition of individual responsibility for school reform. Teacher leaders do not wait to be appointed to a formal role before they offer their expertise and influence to others in order to impact the educational experience. We believe teachers are leaders when they function in professional learning communities to affect student learning; contribute to school improvement; inspire excellence in practice; and empower stakeholders to participate in educational improvement.

The present curriculum and methodology should be reframed to develop self-confidence in students & staff members to face the challenges and solve the problems of self, others and administration.

Key words: Communication, Administration, Skill, Proficiency, feelings, soft skill, language, Expression, professionally

INTRODUCTION

The communication and soft skills are of utmost important to succeed professionally. In the age of globalization, privatization and of the internet these skills help an individual to excel or succeed in the workplace. Soft skills are nothing but the ability of an individual to deal with one's own feelings at the same time understanding the feelings of others. Thus it is a personal mannerism which enriches communicative and interactive capability of an individual. Thus soft skill is basically a sociological concept which stands for an individual's Emotional Intelligence.

Today, the schools and colleges are blaming parents to teach soft skills to the students and on the other hand, parents are blaming colleges and universities for not providing proper training to their children in the domain of communication and soft skills. As a result of this fight, the students are the real sufferers. Though today young graduates are competent academically but poor in communication, soft skills, and etiquettes. The skill or the ability to communicate and express opinions effectively is completely missing amongst young scholars.

In India, the biggest challenge for administration is to enhance the communication and soft skills of the employee and to make them employable. The field of education always proves to be the building pillar of the country. Therefore, many numbers of students has always get attracted towards education as a career. Increasing number of applicants giving entrance exam to be eligible and enroll themselves for many educational branches. Through out of their course, they are taught or trained in a specific branch theoretically as well as practically. Thus they have the required technical background for the job market. However, just hard skills are not sufficient to make them employable. There lies the real essence of the success, that is mastery over communication and soft skills which are equally essential not optional to make them 'corporate ready'.

Today, companies are deliberately investing more and more money on soft skills training since it is not properly included in the academic curriculum anywhere in the engineering education stream. Thus companies are taking

initiatives to groom and develop the personality of their employees to improve their appearance and performance. Thus, there is a great need to refurbish the curriculum of education to maintain a good balance between knowledge and proficiency because education has to work in a group, has to deal with work pressures, report to someone, indulge in presentations, attend phone calls, send mails just to mention a few. In this entire situation, technical skills should be accompanied by communication and soft skills to make them in a real sense. Thus, there is a great need to enhance the performance of students & employees in the corporate sector through the effective use of communication and soft skills.

This paper points out the importance of special educators' communication skills in effective collaboration. The basic components of face-to-face communication are discussed, emphasizing the roles of speaking and listening. The process of active listening is view of particular importance. It considers the impact of various methods of improving public communication skills on critical thinking. The results indicate that communication instruction improves the critical thinking ability of the participants." The authors concluded that " For participation demonstrated the largest positive impact on critical thinking improvement, which provides important evidence to support the maintenance of forensics programs in an era of increased educational accountability, downsizing, and budgetary cutbacks."

The paper argues that educators play an essential role in the development of these skills, and concludes, "Students should learn to see reading and writing as vital support for the most direct way that citizens can express themselves and participate in public life—as public speakers. Public speaking was the primary medium for participation in public affair sat the birth of democracy in ancient Athens, and today public dialogue or argument is, for most citizens, the chief means for participating in public life."

NEED OF COMMUNICATION & SOFT SKILL

Communication skills provide the ladder to the managers and leaders for rapid progression in their careers. In managerial or business context, it is the science and art of communicating. Etymologically, communication as a word is derived from the word "common" in English or "Communes" from Latin. It means "shared by" or "concerning all". Thus communication is a process of "influencing others" to achieve common, shared objectives. These goals could be that of individuals, families, teams, departments / functions and companies. Communication has emerged as a very powerful personal skill that individuals must acquire to be able to perform their duties and become efficient managers and effective leaders.

(1) Communication and Power

Communication is also the most powerful input resource in an enterprise.

The various resources, just to recount, are as below:

- Men
- Money
- Materials
- Machines
- Methods
- Management
- Measurement
- Motive Power

Motivational Leadership Messaging has emerged as the most important resource for, without it, nothing can be transacted anywhere. It is the lifeline of any society. It is the glue that holds companies, communities and countries together. There is another process that is also used to influence others – it is the use of authority or power. They say if person has power it shows because it quickly shows his influence or hold on others opinion. However, it must be understood in its proper perspective. Power has been described as a process of influencing others to do something that left to themselves, they will not do". This process is, then, quite different from that of communication where we influence others as equals - members of the family, members of the inter-departmental teams or customers or fellow members of an association. The process of communication is greatly dependent on the skill of individuals who, as equal members, are in a position to influence others so as to compel, propel or impel them to work together to achieve common goals!

(2) Communication as a two-way process

Communication is a complete process - it starts with communicators sending messages to receivers. An experienced sender of message, whether oral or written, would think of the audience as his customer. He would try to gauge or guess the kind of level of communication the receiver is comfortable with. Thereafter, he would craft his message in a manner and in the language, words, phrases and idioms that the receiver is familiar with. Each receiver of message is really a customer whose needs and wants should be as well known to the sender as it happens in a market place. Obviously, like the sender who chooses words, phrases and idioms from his vocabulary depending on own learning, experience and exposure; receiver also has his own mental filter that is the product of his learning, experience and exposure. To absorb the message in his mind, he does the abstraction of the message in to words, phrases and idioms that he is familiar with or has command over. This leads to his formulating his response to the message received. Once again, it goes through the mind filter and ultimately comes out of the communicatee and starts its return journey to the sender of the message. It conveys back what is understood by the receiver. A sensitive speaker is able to judge the reaction of his audience from the gestures,

sounds and expressions of the audience – the way they sit, the way they yawn or the way they twitter their fingers etc. It is thus a complete cycle because it is a two way process. Until the full process has been gone through the process of communication is considered to be incomplete.

(3) Information as a one-way process

Information flow is another related process. Information is knowledge; it comes from the processing of raw data which records the events as they take place in every miniscule of an organization or an institution. Knowledge is power. The flow of information is considered to be an extremely powerful tool at the disposal of men at all levels of a business enterprise. However, difference between communication and information flows must be understood clearly. Whereas communication is a two way process, information is a one-way process. It is, therefore, half of the process. Yet it is used very extensively in organizations. As businesses grow in size, complexity and dynamics, it is very difficult to ensure two way process all the time. Much of the time, information flows one way – downwards, upwards or horizontal along formal lines of command. These lines of command become the channels of information flows and serve as the cornerstones of communication, coordination and control.

(4) Communication 24 x 7

Knowledge and understanding of the subject of communication is growing very rapidly. Considering that people communicate all the time, round the clock or at least during their waking hours, they must learn how to use this abundant resource for business, personal life and society to their greatest advantage. By doing so, they shall be able to achieve their objectives proactively. In business, this ability, if harnessed fully, will help managers / leaders understand their customers, colleagues and competitors better and will enable them to reorient their strategies, policies and tactics in every day working. As a result national economy and global market shall benefit considerably, enabling them to take the benefits of economic development to the remotest and the most disadvantaged segments of our planet.

While communication skills are commonly recognized as vital to success in business, students still often underestimate how essential some of these skills may be to their careers. In particular, this study reveals that business students underestimate how much of their time may be spent in meetings, the importance of international communication skills, how often they may have to interact with other employees, the importance of oral presentations, and the ability to use multimedia technology. A more realistic awareness of the importance of these skills might motivate students to prepare more carefully for their communication lives in the workplace.

Scope & Objectives of Communication & Soft Skill

The objective of this paper is to present the impact of communication skills and soft skills on the school administration along with the hard skills to achieve their goals as managers. This paper has made an attempt to:

- Focus on Communication Skills required for administration in schools.
- Focus on Soft Skills required for the students in educational institution.
- To emphasize on the importance of communication skills and soft skills in the management area
- To show the relationship between soft skills and job opportunities.
- To show the relationship between soft skills, communications skills in achieving better grades and API in educational institution.
- To show the relationship between soft skills, communications skills to content and academic satisfaction in completion of the management course.

Importance of Communication & Soft Skill

The most dramatic improvements in communication competence were seen in four specific areas:

- (1) feeling confident about oneself,
- (2) feeling comfortable with others' perceptions of you,
- (3) reasoning with people, and
- (4) using language appropriately.

Feeling Confident about Oneself

Soft skills play a vital role for professional success; they help one to excel in the workplace and their importance cannot be denied in this age of information and knowledge. Good soft skills -- which are in fact scarce -- in the highly competitive corporate world will help you stand out in a milieu of routine job seekers with mediocre skills and talent. Soft skills are learned behaviors which require training and focused application. Soft skills will enable students with a strong conceptual and practical framework to build, develop and manage teams. They play an important role in the development of the students' overall personality, thereby enhancing their career prospects. Training in soft skills provides strong practical orientation to the students and help them in building and improving their skills in communication, the effective use of English, business correspondence,

presentations, teambuilding, leadership, time management, group discussions, interviews and interpersonal skills.

It helps students to feel confident in career visioning and planning, effective resume writing and dealing with placement consultants and head hunters. In an age when relationships between individuals and organizations are getting more and more complex, it is not enough to only have an excellent IQ.

Feeling Comfortable with Others

Being good at number crunching and scoring high marks in subjects are not the only criteria for success in professional or personal life. The ability to deal with one's feelings and understand the feelings of others in any given situation helps one to complement academic intelligence/ cognitive capacities (IQ) with a humane understanding of issues. This ability is known as Emotional Intelligence or Soft Skills. Soft Skills have two parts. One part involves developing attitudes and attributes, and the other part involves fine-tuning communication skills to express attitudes, ideas and thoughts well. Attitudes and skills are integral to soft skills. Each one influences and complements the other. Companies are looking for candidates who are smart and can present themselves well. Soft Skills training has become a must for the students who want to go for job or higher studies. Soft skill is not a visible skill like the domain subject content in a student but it helps in improving the personality of the person. It gives finishing touch to the personality. It includes communication skills, interpersonal skills, group dynamics, team work, body language, etiquettes, selling skills, presentation skills, confidence building etc. Soft skills along with grammar, pronunciation and vocabulary exercises will boost the confidence and comfortable with others.

Reasoning with People

Hard skills are academic skills, experience and level of expertise while soft skills are self developed, interactive, communicative, human and transferable skills. Literature suggests that hard skills contribute to only 15% of one's skills success while remaining 85% is made by soft skills. Most employers these days want to hire, retain and promote persons who are dependable, resourceful, ethical, self-directed having effective communication, Instead of just focusing on meeting academic requirements and earning their diplomas, students would do well to strive towards mastering soft skills, too, such as good time management, being accountable and having a strong work ethics.

Soft skills will help the students increase their employability potential and face the challenges of the present time. The students will develop diverse range of abilities and reasoning with people such as communication, strategic-planning, self-awareness, analytical thinking, leadership, teambuilding etc. Soft skills help in improving human potential. Soft skills for students increase their comfort level. It is the acronym for situational awareness, presence, authenticity, clarity and empathy. Team debates, team presentations and self-reflections are essential for developing soft skills. Soft skills play a crucial role in making students employable as it enables them to be flexible, positive to change, handle ever-increasing expectations of employers and to stay globally competitive. Soft skills include concepts such as problem solving, team work and adaptability to change.

These skills are not necessarily graded in a traditional sense but might be assessed with analytical rubrics. The workforce profile defines 'Soft skills' as personal traits and skills that employers seek in employees for jobs of any type. Soft skills are intangible qualities required for full development of an individual. Grooming of the students with soft skills will enable them to successfully take part effectively in various selection procedures, and very many situations they are likely to come across in their professional careers and make them ready to get a head start in the corporate world. It has been observed that the students who performed well in group discussions, mock interviews and oral presentations and who demonstrated communication, critical thinking and group skills during the practice sessions were successful in campus recruitment.

Using Language Appropriately

Over the past decade the importance of soft skills such as communication, presentation and negotiation for b-school students has been emphasized by b-school departments in the developed countries. In this rapidly changing globalized world b-schools do not belong to any particular nation. The students should have the globalized multi skills including communication skills, critical thinking skills, group skills and interpersonal skills. In the world of work, hard skills normally refer to technical or administrative procedures related to an organization's business. Examples include financial procedures and sales administration, using tools, operating machinery, typing, proficiency with software applications and computer protocols, mathematical ability, safety standards. These skills are typically easy to observe, quantify and measure. They are also easier to train, because most of the time the skill sets are brand new to the learner and no unlearning is involved. By contrast, soft skills are typically more difficult to observe, quantify and measure. Some people make friends easily, for example, which would be considered a valuable soft skill in the world of sales. Others are extremely punctual, or able to make rational decisions under pressure.

A person may also have the ability to work with co-workers from other cultures, or learn a new language quickly. These would all be often considered as innate skills. As a matter of fact, soft skills refer to a cluster of qualities, habits, personality traits, attitudes and social graces which everyone possesses in varying degrees, and are needed for everyday life as much as they are needed for work. Communication refers to the exchange of thoughts and ideas with the intention of conveying information. As Robert Gately says, "Effective Communications starts with listening". A teacher, who is able to communicate well with students, can inspire them to listen and participate in class. Students learn at their own pace and assess their proficiency by listening to audio and video materials to develop their listening, speaking, reading and writing skills.

Language Laboratories are necessary for the effective teaching of English pronunciation and communication skills. A language lab acts as a platform for learning, practicing and producing language skills through interactive lessons and communication mode of teaching. The uses of Language Research Centers are considered to be a radical shift from the teacher-centered approach to an independent and enjoyable learning experience. Learners can act and respond in a variety of ways at their own pace.

The language laboratory exists to help one to use technology effectively to communicate. According to numerous surveys, approximately 85% percent of our success in life is directly attributable to our communication and relationship building skills. When you're trying to connect with the majority of people, you feel hesitating. Sometimes you get stuck between two: Open Environment and Closed Environment. Open Environment is characterized with the trust to express different opinions and disagreements, all ideas are seriously considered here, Communication flows in all directions etc.

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